

RIGHTS OF STATELESS PERSONS UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW

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Abstract

Statelessness remains one of the most profound legal and human rights concerns. The study highlights the rights granted to stateless individuals by varying legal frameworks, and how these rights are observed practically. Although international law remains progressive in this regard, rights of stateless persons continue to be in a legal limbo because of lack of implementation, weak enforcement mechanisms and discriminatory nationality laws. The article highlights the reasons due to which these rights have not been enforced as hoped and suggests effective measures to enhance the implementation of these rights.

1. Introduction

Nationality denotes the affiliation between a state and an individual which includes certain privileges and duties. Conversely, stateless persons lack legal recognition and protection of the law. Today, since almost every human right is administered by the state, statelessness means they are being denied basic rights, including the right to education, healthcare, work and political participation. UNHCR recognized over 4.4 million people as stateless in 2024, however, the figure is likely to be much higher, because of underreporting.¹

The problem of statelessness is neither new nor accidental. It is deeply rooted in legacy of colonialism, where discriminatory nationality laws, gender inequality, and forced displacement was predominant. Statelessness represents a failure of both domestic and international legal frameworks that affirm the right of nationality to every individual. Despite numerous treaties and conventions addressing this issue, stateless persons continue to exist in almost every region of the world, often living invisible lives in legal limbo.

The primary question of this research is *what rights do the stateless persons hold in international law, and to what extent these rights are observed in practice?* To address the question, the study follows a doctrinal methodology by examining primary treaties, case laws, UN resolutions and academic writings. It focuses particularly on the Convention of 1954 and 1961 relating to statelessness and other relevant international and domestic standards for addressing

¹ UNHCR. (2025). Global forced displacement. Global Trends: Forced Displacement in 2024, 6-33. <https://doi.org/10.18356/9789211543605c002>

this challenge. The study further examines human rights instruments and the role of UNHCR, International Court of Justice (ICJ) and regional human rights courts such as ECtHR and IACtHR.

This article highlights instances in which stateless people are promised protection by the law but fails to deliver practically. For this reason, primary causes of statelessness and the obstacles faced by people are examined, and realistic solutions are proposed to improve the efficacy of international frameworks, as statelessness directly affects public policy, international humanitarian and human rights standards, and refugee protection laws. A stateless person is cut off from society and state protection when they lose their nationality. According to Hannah Arendt, a political theorist of the twentieth century, someone who lacks nationality is *the rightless being*, barred from the political inclusion, and denied the fundamental *right to have rights*.²

The article proceeds by tracing the historical development of the international legal frameworks on statelessness, which is followed by the analysis of *de jure* and *de facto* statelessness, principles of *jus soli* and *jus sanguinis*, their treatment under international conventions, and the contemporary challenges of enforcement and remedies.

2. Historical Background of Statelessness

Statelessness emerged alongside the concept of nationality itself. The shift of legislative reforms in the early twentieth century from non-codified to codified nationality laws created legal disputes and arbitrary deprivation which renders a considerable number of population lacking valid citizenship.

The earliest attempt at the international level was the Hague Convention of 1930 related to the conflict of nationality laws which provided that everyone should have right to nationality and statelessness should be avoided in the interest of international community.³ Nevertheless, after international conflicts, this early endeavor failed to stop the increasing rate of statelessness. Despite being binding international treaty for its signatories, it lacked enforcement mechanism. Millions of people were uprooted or had their nationality revoked during the two World Wars, which made the situation worse. As a result, first the League of Nations and then the United Nations were established which provided more tangible solutions such as Nansen passports. However, statelessness was officially acknowledged as a humanitarian legal crisis which led to the foundation of International Refugee Organization (IRO) in 1946 and UNHCR in 1950.

Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) passed by UNGA following the horrors of WWII addressed statelessness by stating that nationality rights of any person should not be arbitrarily deprived,⁴ thus it is established that the right of nationality is universal for every

² Hannah Arendt. (1951). The Origins of Totalitarianism. <https://cheirif.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/hannah-arendt-the-origins-of-totalitarianism-meridian-1962.pdf>

³ League of Nations. (1930). Convention on Certain Questions Relating to the Conflict of Nationality Law. <https://www.refworld.org/legal/agreements/lon/1930/en/17955>

⁴ United Nations General Assembly. (1948). Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Art 15. <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>

individual. Two subsequent conventions including the Convention of 1954 governing the status of stateless persons and the Convention of 1961 for reducing statelessness were solely focused on issue of statelessness, its addressal and recognition, rights of stateless people and measures for restricting the initiation of statelessness. By accepting nationality as a topic of international concern and addressal, these accords signaled a paradigm shift from considering this issue exclusively of global well-being rather than a domestic concern. Despite these advancements at a global level, implementation remain a matter of concern because of regional differences and political interests and opposition of the states, ultimately compromising the universality of right to nationality. For instance, Rohingya in Bangladesh and the Bidoon in Kuwait, are still invisible before law.

Judicial interpretation of nationality rights was first offered by ICJ in *Liechtenstein v Guatemala in 1955* where the court emphasized that citizenship rights are not a mere privilege but indication of social engagement and obligation, and stated that nationality must reflect an actual relationship between the state and individual.⁵ This judgement highlighted the importance of nationality in international legal personhood even though it dealt with diplomatic protection of individuals rather than statelessness per se.

It is a fact that statelessness still exists today which shows that this issue is fundamentally legal and political in nature. Gender biases, exclusions based on ethnicity, and historical injustices by states are still reflected in contemporary nationality laws. Because of these factors, the aspirational framework of international law frequently clashes with states' restrictive nationality policies, leaving millions of people in legal complexities that negates the universal values of equality, freedom and dignity which are the foundational basis on which international legal order was established.

3. Mechanisms of De Jure and De Facto Statelessness

The differentiation between de jure and de facto statelessness is relatively important in order to comprehend the regimes available for the protection of stateless persons. Under the Convention of 1954 a person is said to be stateless if a state does not consider him national under its legal operations.⁶ This definition include those individuals who are de jure stateless, or without nationality in the strict legal sense. The principles of *jus soli* and *jus sanguinis*, which leaves people with no nationality, may be the root cause of this. Whether a person is awarded citizenship or not is determined by these two principles. *Jus soli* means law of the land, where the most acknowledged version of the principle holds that birthplace of an individual determines his citizenship. *Jus sanguinis*, on the other hand, states that citizenship is established by the pedigree or parentage of a person, which often comes in contrast with the concept of *jus soli*. According to

⁵ International Court of Justice. (1955). Nottebohm Case (*Liechtenstein v. Guatemala*). <https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/18/018-19550406-JUD-01-00-EN.pdf>

⁶ Bianchini, K. (2018). Protecting Stateless Persons: Strengths and Weaknesses of the 1954 Convention. *Protecting Stateless Persons*, 74-114. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004362901_005

this principle, person having a certain lineage or whose parents, typically the father, is citizen of a particular state should be considered as citizens.

States where nationality laws are influenced by principle of jus sanguinis provides nationality just by being born to a citizen father. A mother cannot pass nationality rights to her offsprings within such territories. Newborns of married, non-stateless parents may be deprived of nationality under specific conditions due to jus sanguinis nationality laws, which solely acknowledge parental descent. Statelessness does not only occur due to Jus sanguinis nationality laws, but it is also passed down from parents to children. Dependent nationality is another prevalent method of this type which refers to the linkage of wife's nationality to her husband, rendering her right contingent upon her husband's right. When these norms are applied, a woman may become stateless upon the death of her husband or due to divorce because under these circumstances, the connection of a wife to a national husband is terminated.⁷ In a similar instance, a woman national of a state which terminates woman's nationality upon marriage would become stateless if she marries a foreigner whose state does not grant nationality rights to wife upon marriage.⁸

However, de facto statelessness occurs when certain individuals are barred from availing state protection despite having nationality rights. Often, those who do not have the same citizenship rights as other law-abiding citizens of the same state are, more than often, referred to as de facto stateless.⁹ As a result, most of these individuals are subjected to state persecution. De facto statelessness usually stems from state discrimination, where de jure statelessness might simply be caused by legislators' oversight by leaving legal loopholes which allow people to fall. Thus, it is not unexpected that de facto and de jure statelessness have different mechanisms. Human trafficking and slavery are two of the main reasons of de facto statelessness. Documents of the victims including passports and birth certificates are confiscated. As a result, they become victim of de facto statelessness. They may be physically far away from availing their state's diplomatic and consular representation or state may deny them because of corruption or lack of resources. Unfortunately, these are not the only reasons which cause de facto statelessness. The practice known as administrative ethnic cleansing, or erasure, is occasionally carried out by governments themselves. In 1992, Slovenian government secretly deleted the records of numerous individuals of Roma from Slovenia's permanent resident databases.¹⁰ The files were transferred from active RPR to the dead. The tactic resulted in erasure of individuals,¹¹ at least on paper, and affected

⁷ International Law Association London conference: Committee on Feminism and International Law. (2000). Final Report on Women's Equality and Nationality in International Law, Page 17. <https://www.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/legacy-pdf/3dc7cccf4.pdf>

⁸ Committee on Feminism and International Law. (2000). Final Report on Women's Equality and Nationality in International Law. <https://www.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/legacy-pdf/3dc7cccf4.pdf>

⁹ Those individuals are not called de facto stateless who are convicted of a crime and because of this crime, denied some right such as right to vote.

¹⁰ Jasminka Dedi. (2003). The Erasure: Administrative Ethnic Cleansing in Slovenia. www.errc.org/cikk.php?cikk=1109&archiv=1

¹¹ Jasminka Dedi. (2003). The Erasure: Administrative Ethnic Cleansing in Slovenia. www.errc.org/cikk.php?cikk=1109&archiv=1

former residents who have left Slovenia due to permanent emigration or death. It appears that the erasure was carried out to prevent non-Slovene Roma from being included in the initial population of the newly formed Republic of Slovenia. The Slovenian government claimed that almost 29,000 people were removed.¹² However, the Helsinki Monitor of Slovenia (HMS) disclosed that the actual figure would be closer to 80,000.¹³ In a similar circumstance, Palestinian refugees who are registered under UNRWA, are not provided effective state protection, as well as thousands of Rohingya Muslims who fled Myanmar, do not possess an official nationality.¹⁴

There are significant legal consequences which occurs in the distinction between these two categories. The 1954 Convention ensures particular rights and status, thus covers de jure class of stateless persons. However, de facto stateless people lies in ambiguous zone of international law, where state discretion and the interpretation of human rights accords frequently determine their protection.¹⁵ The UNHCR and scholarly critics, such as Paul Weis and Laura van Waas, have consistently called on states to assure de facto stateless people with comparable safeguards, claiming that the 1954 Convention's humanitarian protection naturally includes them.¹⁶

Many nations still continue to resist this broad interpretation, arguing that application of 1954 Convention to de facto cases would make it difficult to distinguish between stateless people and refugees. Lack of a consistent definition of statelessness continues to hamper effective identification and protection under domestic laws. As a result, many people continue to be in an unclear and ambiguous category since they are neither recognized as citizens nor refugees and they are invisible to both international and domestic legal regimes.

4. International Legal Framework on Statelessness

4.1 1954 Convention relating to the Status of Stateless Persons

The convention of 1954 provides the foundation for protection of stateless people under International law. It was introduced in order to regulate the position and treatment of stateless individuals in a manner similar to refugees as laid down by the convention of 1951 related to the status of refugees. The primary purpose of the convention is to provide rights to stateless individuals without any discrimination.

¹² Jasminka Dedi. (2003). The Erasure: Administrative Ethnic Cleansing in Slovenia. www.errc.org/cikk.php?cikk=1109&archiv=1

¹³ International Helsinki Federation for Human Rights. (2001). Human Rights in the OSCE Region: The Balkans, The Caucasus, Europe, Central Asia and North America Report (Events of 2000). <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/human-rights-osce-region-balkans-caucasus-europe-central-asia-and-north-america-report>

¹⁴ Fumagalli, M. (2023). Myanmar 2017: The Rohingya crisis between radicalisation and ethnic cleansing. Asia Maior, XXVIII. <https://doi.org/10.52056/9788833130453/10>

¹⁵ Bianchini, K. (2018). Protecting Stateless Persons: Strengths and Weaknesses of the 1954 Convention. Protecting Stateless Persons, 74–114. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004362901_005

¹⁶ Weis, P. (1979). Preface to the Second Edition. Nationality and Statelessness in International Law, XVII–XVII. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004642577_004

Objectives and Core Provisions

The Convention seeks to provide legal status to the stateless people, making their habituation easier, and ensure access to socioeconomic rights. It requires contracting states to provide administrative assistance to stateless people who are legally residing in their territory in terms of documentation.¹⁷ Additionally, it prohibits all forms of discrimination including racial, national, ethnic or religious.

In this regard, Article 5 of the Convention mandates contracting state parties to provide the rights available in the convention without any discrimination. Article 7 stipulates that stateless people must be treated equally like other aliens residing in a state in terms of their legal status. Article 13 ensures the acquisition of movable and immovable property by stateless persons like other aliens residing in a state, leases and other related contracts and rights pertaining thereto in respect to property. Article 17 ensures access to employment opportunities by which they can earn decent wages. Article 24 guarantees social security and labor rights, Article 25 provides administrative assistance in respect to documentation and certification while Article 26 permits freedom of movement inside the host nation.

Despite these assurances, the 1954 Convention does not specifically outline a method for identifying statelessness, thus domestic authorities are primarily responsible for its implementation. This vacuum is filled by the *UNHCR's Handbook on Protection of Stateless Persons (2014)*, which suggests that identification can be made possible by creating equitable and easily accessible statelessness determination procedures (SDPs).¹⁸

Analytical Commentary

The actual efficacy of 1954 Convention remains uneven. There are immense territories where stateless people have no official legal protection because states, including Pakistan, India, and numerous Gulf nations, are not parties to the Convention.¹⁹ Furthermore, compliance to the Convention varies even among signatories, where multiple states have incorporated limited provisions in their national legislation, while others do not provide proper documentation or allow a legitimate stay to stateless people.

The decision of ECtHR in *Rusu v Austria* illuminated the importance of the principles of restorative justice determining stateless people. The Court held that when stateless persons are kept in arbitrary detention without due process, it violates Article 5 of European Convention (ECHR).

¹⁷ Conference of Plenipotentiaries convened by Economic and Social Council resolution 526 A (XVII). (1954). Convention relating to the Status of Stateless Persons, Art 3-6. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-relating-status-stateless-persons>

¹⁸ UNHCR. (2014). Handbook on the Protection of Stateless Persons under 1954 Convention Relating to the Status of Stateless Persons. https://www.unhcr.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/27/2017/04/CH-UNHCR_Handbook-on-Protection-of-Stateless-Persons.pdf

¹⁹ United Nations Treaty Collection. (2026). Status of 1954 Convention Relating to the Status of Stateless Persons. https://treaties.un.org/pages/ViewDetailsII.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=V-3&chapter=5&Temp=mtdsg2&clang=en

This analysis indicates that the rights provided by 1954 Convention are to be read in conjunction with basic human rights principles.²⁰

Nonetheless, the primary flaw of the Convention is its dependence on the goodwill of nations for implementation. It does not impose binding restrictions on state parties to confer permanent residency or nationality. Accordingly, statelessness often leads to prolonged periods of uncertainty as shown by the predicaments faced by the Rohingya in Bangladesh and the Bidoon in Kuwait, both of whom are identified as stateless by the international community yet do not enjoy any legal identity or long-term solution.

4.2 1961 Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness

The convention of 1961 strives to prevent the initiation of statelessness, whereas the 1954 Convention provides safeguards to individuals who are already stateless. The convention provides a detailed framework for the states that how the right of nationality should be granted, sustained, and evacuated in accordance with the standards relating to human rights.

Objectives and Core Provisions

The convention lays out particular protections in order to stop statelessness at birth of a person and later in his life. In this regard, Article 1 in para 1 require states to grant nationality to all the individuals born inside their territories. Article 1 in para 3 provides that children will acquire nationality of a state from their mother if she is a national of that state. Article 4 provides that nationality rights will be provided to a person if any of his parent is national of the state at the time of his birth even if he is not born inside the territory of the state. Article 8 forbids states in depriving someone of their nationality if doing so would make them stateless, with the exception of situations involving fraud or actions that would gravely jeopardize the state's fundamental interests. Similarly, Article 9 provides that a denial of nationality based on national, religious or political backgrounds must be avoided.

The Convention also requires governments to prevent statelessness resulting from state succession, renunciation, or losing nationality rights due to marriage.²¹ These requirements comply with Article 7 of *Convention on the Rights of Child (CRC)* which guarantees right of children to obtain nationality from their parents.

Analytical Commentary

Despite being a major advancement, the efficacy of 1961 Convention is compromised by low ratification rates and the lack of enforcement tools. Major regions, such as South Asia and the

²⁰ European Court of Human Rights. (2008). *Rusu v Austria*, Application no 34082/02. <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-88669#>

²¹ United Nations General Assembly (1961), Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness, Art 6-9. https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/conventions/6_1_1961.pdf

Middle East, remain outside of its legal purview as of 2025, roughly only 80 states are parties to the convention.²²

Political factors also restrict the Convention's influence and implementation. Many states oppose bestowment of instant nationality to stateless people out of their concern for security or demographic ramifications. For instance, the prevention of Rohingya by Myanmar from attaining nationality is a gross violation of the spirit of 1961 Convention, but international instruments failed to make compliance.²³ Pursuant to Article 11 of the Convention, UNHCR is also important for stateless individuals in claiming the benefits of this Convention and assistance by which they can present their problems to the appropriate authority. Its Global Action Plan to End Statelessness (2014-2024) sets ambitious targets, including universal birth registration and an end to childhood statelessness.²⁴ However, greater political will and collaboration between domestic and foreign players is needed to accomplish these objectives at international level.

4.3 Related International and Regional Human Rights Instruments

International instruments of human rights such as ICCPR and CEDAW reinforce the position of stateless persons and provide safeguards for the protection of their rights. In this context, Article 26 of the ICCPR guarantees equality before the law, while Article 24 forbids the arbitrary deprivation of nationality. Likewise, Article 9(2) of Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) requires that contracting states must provide equal rights to women in transferring nationality rights to their children, while the Convention on the Rights of Child (CRC) in Article 7 recognizes the right to name and nationality for every child at its birth.

These right are further reinforced at the regional level through instruments like the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child guarantees in Article 6 that every child has a right to name, birth registration, and nationality without discrimination, while the American Convention on Human Rights in Article 20 ensures right of nationality to every person born in the state's territory. Judicial interpretation of IACtHR in *Yean and Bosico v Dominican Republic*, held that denial of nationality to children (Yean and Bosico) born to Haitian parents violated both the rights of nationality and prevention of racial discrimination.²⁵

In Europe, protection is primarily safeguarded by the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and the European Convention on Nationality (1997). Judicial interpretation if

²² UNHCR. (2014). Global Action Plan to End Statelessness 2014–2024. <https://www.unhcr.org/au/sites/en-au/files/legacy-pdf/54621bf49.pdf>

²³ International Court of Justice. (2021). Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (*The Gambia v. Myanmar*), Provisional Measures. <https://icj-web.leman.un-icc.cloud/sites/default/files/case-related/178/178-20200123-ORD-01-00-EN.pdf>

²⁴ UNHCR (n.d). Global Action Plan to End Statelessness 2.0, Action 2, 7 and 8. <https://www.unhcr.org/what-we-do/protect-human-rights/ending-statelessness>

²⁵ Inter American Court of Human Rights. (2005). *Yean and Bosico v. Dominican Republic*. https://www.corteidh.or.cr/docs/casos/articulos/seriec_130_%20ing.pdf

ECtHR in *Kim v Russia*²⁶ and *Karashev v Finland*²⁷ highlights that the rights of stateless individuals are shielded from discrimination and arbitrary detention under these conventions.

Transition from Legal Norms to Lived Experience

International instruments that form a foundation of legal regime for statelessness were described in the preceding section. However, it is rare for rights that have been granted theoretically to instantly translate into enforceable rights. The discrepancy between official status of stateless people and their treatment under International legal regime continues to be a significant obstacle. Implementation of the 1954 and 1961 Conventions is often selective or largely symbolic, even in those states that are signatories to the Conventions. This section examines the difficulties faced by stateless people which are a manifestation of deprivation and a manner in which international law tries to address this problem.

5. Hurdles and Hardships Faced by Stateless Persons

5.1 Legal Invisibility and Denial of Civil Rights

Lack of legal identity is the most direct consequence faced by stateless persons. They often lack documentation which is required for work, travel, marriage, or owning property in a state where they do not possess nationality.²⁸ They are refused civil registration at birth, which starts a cycle of exclusion that lasts a lifetime. This is exemplified in example of Rohingya in Myanmar, where Rohingya population was denied nationality rights by Citizenship Law of 1982, They were unable to lawfully marry, relocate without a visa, and frequently having their children denied birth certificates. Moreover, they were subjected to starvation, abduction of girls and sexual violence against women and systematic theft during 2017 Myanmar's military operation against Rohingya population.²⁹

During the 1960s and 70s, the Bidoon people, who were formerly nomadic tribes, received economic and social benefits equal to those of Kuwaiti citizens, but labelled as illegal residents in Kuwait due to the political instability of 1980s and 90s.³⁰ They are confined within state territories since they are unable to vote, hold government jobs, or obtain legitimate passports. The Nubians

²⁶ European Court of Human Rights. (2014). *Kim v. Russia*, Application no. 44260/13. <https://caselaw.statelessness.eu/caselaw/ecthr-kim-v-russia>

²⁷ European Court of Human Rights. (1999). *Karashev v. Finland*, Application no. 31414/96. <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng?i=001-4592#>

²⁸ UNHCR. (2014). Global Action Plan to End Statelessness 2014–2024. <https://www.unhcr.org/au/sites/en-au/files/legacy-pdf/54621bf49.pdf>

²⁹ Cheesman, N. (2018). How in Myanmar 'National Races' Came to Surpass Citizenship and Exclude Rohingya. Interpreting Communal Violence in Myanmar, 127–145. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315146263-7>

³⁰ Human Rights Watch. (2011). Prisoners of the Past: Kuwaiti Bidun and the Burden of Statelessness. <https://www.hrw.org/reports/kuwait0611.pdf>

of Kenya, who have lived there for millennia, still denied identity cards, because of legal invisibility.³¹

5.2 Economic Marginalization

Stateless persons are routinely denied access to governmental services, legal employment, and land ownership. Following the 2013 Constitutional Court verdict, tens of thousands of people of Haitian heritage in the Dominican Republic lost their citizenship, making it impossible for them to obtain healthcare or lawful working opportunities.³² Similarly, stateless Kurds in Syria and Lebanon are unable to register enterprises and are denied property rights, which results in generational structural poverty.³³

Stateless people are frequently forced into exploitative labor markets due to economic exclusion. As seen with Rohingya refugees in Cox Bazar of Bangladesh, where their lack of legal status exposes them to maltreatment by local employers and authorities, while many have become exposed to trafficking and forced labor.³⁴

5.3 Denial of Social and Educational Rights

Stateless populations are frequently denied access to healthcare and education, which are core human rights provided under ICESCR.³⁵ Children remain unable to enroll in school or take national exams without identity documents. The committee of African experts in *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa v Kenya*, held that Kenya's denial of nationality to Nubian children violated the provisions of multiple international human rights frameworks including Article 6 of the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, Article 7(1) of CRC and Article 24(3) of ICCPR. As a result, Kenyan Nubians were granted restricted access to public education.³⁶

Many young people in Palestine are unable to study abroad because of their inability to get internationally accepted travel permits due to chronic statelessness, compounded by occupation.³⁷

³¹ Open Society Justice Initiative. (2011). *Nubian Community in Kenya v. The Government of Kenya*. <https://www.justiceinitiative.org/litigation/nubian-community-kenya-v-kenya>

³² [Coat of Arms of the Dominican Republic] Dominican Republic Constitutional Court. (2013). Ruling TC/0168/13. [https://gobiernodanilomedina.do/themes/custom/presidency/docs/gobplan/gobplan-15/TC-168-13-\(english\).pdf](https://gobiernodanilomedina.do/themes/custom/presidency/docs/gobplan/gobplan-15/TC-168-13-(english).pdf)

³³ Albarazi, Z. (2013). The Stateless Syrians. SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2269700>

³⁴ Salehin, M. M. (2024). Gendered Vulnerabilities and Violence in Rohingya Refugee Camps in Bangladesh. *Gendered Vulnerabilities and Violence in Forced Migration*, 69–91. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-62435-3_5

³⁵ General Assembly resolution 2200A (XXI). (1966). International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Art 13-14. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-economic-social-and-cultural-rights>

³⁶ African Committee of Experts on the Rights and Welfare. (2011). *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa (IHRDA) and Open Society Justice Initiative on Behalf of Children of Nubian Descent in Kenya v. The Government of Kenya*. <https://iarmj.africa/case-summary/institute-human-rights-and-development-africa-ihirda-and-open-society-justice>

³⁷ Amnesty International. (2022). Israel's apartheid against Palestinians: A Cruel System of Domination and a Crime against Humanity. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2022/02/israels-apartheid-against-palestinians-a-cruel-system-of-domination-and-a-crime-against-humanity/>

The sense of belonging that nationality typically offers is thus undermined by the denial of social rights, which prolongs poverty and psychological suffering for Palestinians.

5.4 Gender Discrimination and Intergenerational Statelessness

One of the most persistent reasons of statelessness is gender bias in domestic laws. More than 25 states still prohibit women from granting nationality to their offspring, despite Article 9 of CEDAW which mandates that women has equal rights as of women in terms of transferring nationality rights to their children.³⁸ Children born to citizen mothers and foreign fathers are oftenly denied right to nationality in Arab states like Qatar and Lebanon. Survivors of gender-based violence and single mothers are disproportionately affected.

When these discriminatory laws combine with inadequate birth-registration methodologies of the states, statelessness persists from generation to generation. Nearly one out of every four children worldwide, under the age of five, are not registered according to the reports of UNICEF.³⁹ This statistic is relatively higher in low-income and conflict-affected nations correlated with statelessness.

5.5 Psychological and Political Exclusion

Statelessness causes severe psychological suffering such as sentiments of skepticism, embarrassment and loss of identity, in addition to material hardship. Stateless people are compelled to live in constant fear of being arbitrarily detained or deported as they are unable to avail themselves of state protection. Political exclusion, which keeps stateless persons from taking part in civic life, voting, or joining political parties, makes this suffering even worse. As a result, stateless individuals exist outside of the social contract that unites citizens and states.

Human Rights Watch interviewed a Palestinian refugee who expressed the lack of political agency by stating, *we are like ghosts; we are seen, but we don't exist*. This statement is the aftershock of the statement of Prime Minister of Israel Benjamin Netanyahu, posted on Instagram in 2019, which stated that Israel is the nation-state of the Jewish people only, it should not be considered state for all of its citizens.⁴⁰ These chronicles highlight the fact that statelessness is a lived state of rightlessness and mental agony rather than just a legal classification.

6. Implementation of Remedies under International Law

6.1 Role of UN and UNHCR

Article 11 of the 1961 Convention assigns UNHCR with the responsibility of assisting states and individuals in ending statelessness. Over the years, the UNHCR has evolved from a refugee-

³⁸ Article 9(2) of CEDAW states that contracting states shall grant equal rights to women like men in terms of nationality rights of their children.

³⁹ van der Straaten, J. (2020). Birth Registration for Every Child by 2030: Are we on track? Review and Annotated Version of an Unhelpful UNICEF Publication. SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3657062>

⁴⁰ Human Rights Watch. (2021). A Threshold Crossed: Israeli Authorities and the Crimes of Apartheid and Persecution. <https://www.hrw.org/report/2021/04/27/threshold-crossed/israeli-authorities-and-crimes-apartheid-and-persecution>

focused organization to the institution that proposes initiatives to avoid and lessen statelessness. UNHCR's #IBelong Campaign (2014–2024) is a global strategy built on action points, such as universal birth registration and the elimination of discrimination from domestic laws related to nationality.⁴¹

UNHCR's Handbook on Protection of Stateless Persons provides technical guidance for the establishment of Statelessness Determination Procedures (SDPs). States including the Philippines, Spain, and UK have identified and regularized stateless individuals using these SDPs.⁴² However, the absence of a legally mandated obligation requiring states to establish SDPs limits its reach. Recognition of statelessness is entirely discretionary in many states, including Pakistan and most of the Gulf states due to lack of enforcement mechanisms.

6.2 Domestic Legal Remedies and Judicial Developments

Domestic courts play a significant role in interpreting international obligations of states related to statelessness. In this regard, Inter American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR) in *Yean and Bosico v Dominican Republic*, ordered the Republic to provide nationality rights to children who had been wrongfully denied due to racial discrimination. Similarly, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) in *Kim v Russia*, found that the uncertain detention of a stateless person violated Article 5 of the ECHR, thus emphasized proportionality and procedural safeguards for them.

Similarly, the ECOWAS Court of Justice's ruling in *Hadijatou Mani Koraou v Niger*, which involved slavery, emphasized that lack of nationality renders individuals vulnerable to exploitation and urged states to provide adequate measures for prevention and entitled the applicants to an all-inclusive compensation for the harm caused by slavery.⁴³ These judicial interpretations demonstrates expanding understanding on statelessness that it is more than merely an administrative variation involving serious infringement of human rights.

6.3 Soft-Law Instruments and International Cooperation

Soft law instruments such as Universal Periodic Review (UPR), UN General Assembly resolutions, and Human Rights Council recommendations are persuasive mechanisms for accountability of states in case of violations. In resolution 20/5 of 2012, Human Rights Council reaffirmed the right of nationality and called upon authorities not to arbitrarily deprive stateless

⁴¹ UNHCR. (2014). #IBelong Campaign to End Statelessness. <https://www.unhcr.org/what-we-do/protect-human-rights/ending-statelessness/ibelong-campaign-end-statelessness>

⁴² UNHCR. (2020). Good Practice Papers Action 6: Establishing Statelessness Determination Procedures for the Protection of Stateless Persons. <https://emergency.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/2023-12/UNHCR%2C%20Good%20Practices%20Paper%20Action%206%20-%20Establishing%20Statelessness%20Determination%20Procedures%20for%20the%20Protect%20of%20Stateless%20Persons%2C%20July%202020.pdf>

⁴³ Community Court of Justice of the Economic Community of West African States. (2008). ECW/CCJ/JUD/06/08 *Hadijatou Mani Koraou v. Niger*. <https://caselaw.ihrrda.org/api/files/15247466200936pmq64mcg518qtoxs3iejyvi.pdf>

persons.⁴⁴ A number of states, including Kenya and Thailand, committed to enact reforms to reduce statelessness for minority groups following the 2019 UPR sessions. The latter operates as a touchstone that conditions domestic debate and legislation, whether or not it possesses any coercive power. Academic research shows that birth-registration reforms are most likely to be implemented by states within two years that are subjected to peer reviews under the UPR.⁴⁵

6.4 Global Survey of Statelessness

Europe

The figure is estimated to be around 679,000 in Europe, according to UN. In this regard, the two important treaties adopted by Council, include the European Convention of 1997 regarding Nationality, which has been signed by many states, and the Convention of 2006 for avoiding statelessness.

The biggest concern of Europe is the situation of stateless persons in Roma. These people have marginalized access of opportunities including residence, medicare, and literacy. In multiple states, a small number of these communities have primary education. While in other, they face violence and discrimination. Multiple European states acknowledge that these communities are neglected yet a very little progress have been made on improving the legal and socio-economic status of these communities.

Populations of former Soviet Union have also faced the issue of statelessness. Although situation has improved considerably, a large number of Russian speakers in Baltic states have gone through discrimination in state policies that marginalized their nationality rights. Meskhetian Turks in the Krasnodar Territory of Russia have been denied nationality rights and subjected to violence. However, U.S. resettled several thousand people of this community from 2004-2007 which is a positive development. Similarly, the states which emerged from Yugoslavia are trying to provide the citizenship rights to displaced persons and refugees since the breakup of territory in 1990s. Multiple states have took a positive step by recognizing statelessness and granted citizenship to these individuals. Romania acceded to the two conventions on statelessness in 2006, Austria ratified the Convention of 1954 in 2008 while Finland ratified the Convention of 1961 in the same year. Montenegro ratified the Convention of 1954 relating to the status of stateless individuals in 2013.⁴⁶

Asia

The issue of statelessness continues to exist all over the Asia. One of the most desperate populations in Asia affected by this issue are the Rohingya, a Muslim minority with origin in

⁴⁴ United Nations General Assembly. (2012). Resolution adopted by the Human Rights Council 20/5: Human Rights and Arbitrary Deprivation of Nationality. <https://documents.un.org/doc/resolution/gen/g12/153/11/pdf/g1215311.pdf>

⁴⁵ van Waas, L. (2014). 'Are We There Yet?' The Emergence of Statelessness on the International Human Rights Agenda. *Netherlands Quarterly of Human Rights*, 32(4), 342–346. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016934411403200402>

⁴⁶ Institute on Statelessness and Inclusion. (2014). *The World's Stateless*. <https://files.institutesi.org/worldsstateless.pdf>

Burma. In Burma, citizenship is denied to over 700,000 Rohingyas and they are subjected to religious persecution human rights breaches. Around one million of Rohingyas live in other states while numerous are living in destituted conditions and fear of deportation in states like Japan, Bangladesh, Malaysia and Saudi Arabia as refugees or illegal migrants. There is another community of Indian origin in Burma numbering a half million who is also effectively stateless. A vast number of hill tribe people numbering close to a million in Thailand lack Thai nationality due to considerably short deadlines for filing and partly due to their inability to provide birthplace documentation due to their residence in rural areas. Similarly, children among two million Burmese refugees or migrants in Thailand are effectively stateless as they are ineligible for Thai or Burmese citizenship.

Notable restrictions that have been faced by individuals of Chinese descent regarding citizenship rights in Vietnam, Korea and Indonesia. In eastern Malaysia, a large number of undocumented children in Sabah are believed to be stateless due to their migrant parents which renders them extremely vulnerable in terms of human rights violations, effective on those particularly, whose parents have been deported from other states. In Nepal, hundred thousand of Bhutanese refugees remained in chronic conditions for about twenty years, when U.S. resettled almost 60,000 of these individuals. Additionally, the reluctance of central Asian states in recognizing multiple marginalized communities as refugees in their territories has triggered widespread citizenship insecurity.

Bangladesh has made notable developments where citizenship rights are granted to Urdu speaking community in 2008 through a High Court decision. Their status was disputed since the partition of Bangladesh from Pakistan. Nepal has conducted vigorous registration campaigns which reduced the stateless population from millions to hundreds of thousands in its territory. Central Asian states are still struggling with statelessness, even though the situation has improved considerably. Kazakhstan has made efforts in recent years to reduce obstacles in terms of citizenship rights to relocate Kandas, while Turkmenistan and Kyrgyzstan granted nationality to thousands of people in 2006 and 2007 who departed Tajikistan during civil war of 1992 to 1997.⁴⁷

There are certain groups in India including Chakmas, Hajongs and Punjabis, that are grappling with statelessness or with a substantial risk. These communities were mostly affected by the partition of 1947 which divided the United Subcontinent into two dominions notably India and Pakistan. India has not granted nationality rights to most of the descendants of these communities. Chakmas numbering nearly 65,000, have been given citizenship and voting rights however, the government systematically deprives them from accessing socio-economic and political rights.

Nearly 4 million Afghan refugees are residing in Pakistan including 1.4 million of those having PoR cards and an estimated 1.4 million holding Afghan Citizen Cards. There is no official

⁴⁷ Brad K. Blitz. (2009). Statelessness, protection and equality. <https://www.onlinelibrary.iihl.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Statelessness-protection-and-equality.pdf>

data regarding how many undocumented Afghans are residing in Pakistan, but unofficial estimates suggests that this number is around 1.7 million. They are effectively stateless as they lack nationality and identity papers which curtail their freedom to claim healthcare, education or legal employment. This number has decreased significantly since 2023 but huge wave of deportation of these undocumented migrants back to Afghanistan in late 2025 created uncertainty.

Africa

This problem exists almost all over the Africa where most of the African nations refuse to grant nationality rights to children through their mothers because of *jus sanguinis* nationality laws. Over 3.5 million people in Côte d'Ivoire do not have identification documents where the situation leads to render these people vulnerable to human rights breaches. People of Sahrawi origin have resided in Algeria without citizenship rights since 1980 while their number stays between 110,000 and 155,000. The Egypt faces a major issue with stateless children who become stateless because of their fathers not having Egyptian citizenship.

On the other hand, there have been notable positive changes in Mauritania, Ethiopia and Kenya. Nubian community residing in Kenya face minimal constraints in national registration recently. Ethiopia has made notable efforts in enabling Eritreans to reinstate their Ethiopian citizenship which was forfeited during border skirmishes with Eritrea from 1998 to 2000. Egypt has made encouraging efforts in 2003 for speedy processing of nationality applications of individuals having biracial heritage however, the progress remained slow in compared to the people affected. Encouragingly, both Senegal and Rwanda have ratified conventions of 1954 and 1961. The UN-supported transitional government in Côte d'Ivoire launched a mobile identification program which reported that about 16% of applicants are at high risk of statelessness. It was unanimously agreed in 2008 that national elections would only take place after this identification process is completed.⁴⁸

The Americas

The biggest concern in Americas in this regard are the individuals of Haitian and Colombian origin. Children of around one million people of Haitian origin residing in the Dominican Republic, are often deprived of citizenship and excluded from public services. Similar problems are faced by children of same origin in Bahamas and other Caribbean states. Individuals of Colombian origin having no documentation does not have state protection in Ecuador while stateless individuals face problems in child registration in states like in Venezuela and Panama.

⁴⁸ Bronwen Manby. (2020). Legal Identity for All and Statelessness: Opportunity and Threat at the Junction of Public and Private International Law. https://researchonline.lse.ac.uk/id/eprint/108196/1/Manby_Legal_Identity_Statelessness_SCR_2020_002_.pdf

States like Bahamas, Mexico and Costa Rica and have made access to citizenship even more difficult with unreasonable sets of requirements, including tight deadlines or contrasting conditions for outlanders and non-natives.

Canada took notable steps back in 2008 when it started accommodating isolated Vietnamese families that are stranded in Philippines for nearly two decades. Meanwhile, no other state had accepted them since the Fall of Saigon. Similarly, Brazil and Belize have formally adopted both the conventions of 1954 and 1961. It has been reported that around 1,000 to 3,000 stateless persons are residing in Brazil. Fortunately, Brazil has recognized this problem and aimed to rectify the situation. In these efforts, it revised its Constitution and signed both the conventions.⁴⁹

Middle East

Most of the Middle East states discriminate in granting equal nationality rights to women. Women who marry non-citizens render their children stateless because they do not obtain citizenship rights from their parents as per state laws. There are three main groups that are facing the threat of statelessness in this region which includes Palestinians, Kurds and Bidun.

Varying forms of obstacles such as legal standing and residential rights exist for Palestinians all across the Middle East. Palestinian refugees are internationally recognized by The United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestinian Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA). The people who existed in Palestine from 1946 before losing their homes during the 1948 Arab Israeli war are known as Palestinians. However, UNRWA recognizes Palestinian refugees through a definition that involves male descendants which is estimated to be the population of around 4.6 million. According to the 1954 Convention, individuals collaborative support from other UN bodies such as UNHCR are beyond the jurisdiction of convention. Due to this reason, the convention does not apply to a large number of these refugees because they are receiving assistance from UNRWA. Nonetheless, millions of these refugees have no nationality rights, even though a small number have been granted nationality in other states.

Kurd community is estimated to be around 25 to 30 million all over the globe where more than half Kurdish community is residing in Turkey. While, the remaining is residing in states like Syria, Iran, Iraq, Armenia, Lebanon and Azerbaijan. Tens of thousands of Kurds in Lebanon and hundreds of thousands in Syria and have no nationality rights. Numerous Kurdish people have moved from Iran to Iraq due to favorable provisions in the improvised constitution of Iraq related to nationality.⁵⁰

The Bidun population is a demographically dispersed group with a presence in multiple Middle Eastern states including Qatar, Bahrain, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirates.

⁴⁹ Bronwen Manby. (2020). Legal Identity for All and Statelessness: Opportunity and Threat at the Junction of Public and Private International Law. https://researchonline.lse.ac.uk/id/eprint/108196/1/Manby_Legal_Identity_Statelessness_SCR_2020_002_.pdf

⁵⁰ Institute on Statelessness and Inclusion. (2014). The World's Stateless. <https://files.institutesi.org/worldsstateless.pdf>

Encouraging steps have been taken by United Arab Emirates in order to formalize their citizenship status by registration and naturalizing process, notably in 2006 and 2008.

7. Research Findings

The study reveals that, although being strongly addressed by international law, statelessness continues to exist mostly because of domestic inertia and political reluctance rather than lacking legal principles. A thorough foundational framework has been established by the Conventions of 1954 and 1961 and above mentioned human rights frameworks, but enforcement is still dispersed. This analysis reveals a number of hurdles.

First, it is still difficult in domestic practice to distinguish between de jure and de facto statelessness. De facto stateless people lack legal status and protection in many states even though the intact procedures are available to recognize them. National authorities hardly follow UNHCR guidelines, even when they do exist.

Second, the main root cause of statelessness is discrimination in nationality laws. As demonstrated by Rohingya, Bidoon, and Dominicans of Haitian heritage, generational cycles of statelessness are sustained by ethnic and gender inequality in citizenship laws of various states. The unequal transfer of nationality by women persists despite the obligatory provisions of CEDAW and CRC for contracting state parties.

Third, the instruments that are devised for implementation are weak. The UNHCR's mandate under 1961 convention lacks coercive power and its campaigns rely on voluntary state collaboration. Regional courts such as ECtHR and IACtHR have developed jurisprudence by linking statelessness with human rights breaches despite their geographical limitations.

Fourth, statelessness results in multiple forms of deprivation, including lack of access to healthcare, work, education, political participation and psychological well-being. Hannah Arendt's observation that stateless people become 'the rightless beings on the earth' is confirmed by this scenario, that essentially removes stateless people from the legal order.

Finally, several trends show positive signs, yet they remain impartial. The continuous advocacy efforts in Brazil and Nepal and Côte d'Ivoire have led to successful progress in legislative changes. However, such advancements will remain localized as long as the Conventions are not universally ratified and their provisions are not incorporated into national legislation.

8. Conclusion

The right to nationality lies at the intersection of human dignity and sovereignty. This article shows that statelessness has long been acknowledged by international law as anomaly in conflict with the fundamental ideas of equality and dignity. The convention of 1954 guarantees the minimum standards of protection for stateless people, while the Convention of 1961 aims to stop future incidents of statelessness. The two conventions together create a coordinated legal framework

when it is combined with other regulatory instruments such as ICCPR, ICESCR, CRC, and CEDAW.

However, actual application is not as advanced as compared to the law. Right to nationality is utilized as a political tool by states, either to remove minorities or to restrict immigration. Ratification and implementation are still very far apart. The study thus confirms that the true difficulty is pragmatic rather than conceptual, thus requiring international commitments into domestic frameworks with efficient supervision.

Human rights breaches are both a cause and an effect of statelessness. It must be acknowledged that citizenship rights are required for exercising almost all fundamental rights and they are not merely an administrative designation. Therefore, protecting stateless people should be viewed as a legal obligation resulting from the universality of human rights rather than as charity.

9. Recommendations

1. Universal Ratification and Domestic Incorporation

Every state need to ratify the Conventions of 1954 and 1961, and their provisions should be incorporated into domestic legislation. Domestic laws need to establish procedures for statelessness recognition and provide identification methods for stateless people to secure their rights.

2. Establishment of Statelessness Determination Procedures (SDPs)

The UNHCR guidelines require states to create autonomous organizations which must provide unbiased claim evaluation and offer stateless people judicial access and legal representation.

3. Reform of Discriminatory Nationality Laws

States should be obligated to remove racial and gender-based barriers to citizenship. Women need to obtain the same nationality rights as men and children who face statelessness must receive citizenship rights.

4. Strengthened International and Regional Cooperation

Data exchange, institutional development, and periodic peer review should be coordinated by the UN and regional organizations, and civil society actors should be obligated to use tools like the Universal Periodic Review (UPR).

5. Integration and Naturalization Pathways

After a valid stay, host states should make it easier for stateless people to obtain opportunities related to healthcare, work, and education. They should also offer clear pathways to citizenship and permanent residence to these individuals.

6. Enhanced Judicial Remedies and Monitoring

States should acknowledge the role of international organizations, such as Human Rights Committee, having authority to hear issues relating to nationality. The creation of a dedicated international tribunal on statelessness may be considered.

7. Awareness and Civil-Registration Campaigns

The most effective strategies to stop future cases of statelessness are universal birth registration and public education on the topic. Digital and community-based registration systems should be endorsed and funded by the states.

8. Research and Data Transparency

Academics and regional NGOs should collaborate to produce reliable statistics on stateless populations across the globe in shaping evidence-based policy rather than politically driven narratives of the states.

If these recommendations are implemented effectively, these measures have the potential to transform the aspirational language of the *#IBelong Campaign* into a concrete, worldwide reality where every individual will have nationality and can enjoy the benefits of protection it provides.

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